

Quantum Mechanics, Reality, and the Many-Worlds Interpretation: Experimentalism and the Ontological Aspects of the Interpretation

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Abstract: We study the ontological aspects of the Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics through statistical/empirical assessments. It is shown that the interpretation collapses on a single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics at classical limits.

Keywords: Many-Worlds Interpretation, Born Rule, Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle, Experimental Errors, Statistical Interpretation, The MWI Gamble.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI) of Quantum Mechanics is, in fact, an alternative approach for the wave function collapse mechanism that leads to the existence of multiple parallel worlds, each representing a different outcome of quantum events. In principle, the MWI has been proposed to overcome the confusing ambiguity of the measurement postulate that is commonly assumed to be one of the fundamental concepts of quantum mechanics [15, 17–20].¹ While MWI has gained attention for its elegant resolution of the measurement problem, it faces an extensive amount of criticism when examined through the lens of experimentalism.² The majority of these criticisms center on the physical theory's testability, a quality that the MWI is lacking with current or anticipated experimental capabilities.³ More precisely, although there are several explanations of the MWI⁴ but they all have one problem in common: There is no confidence about the theoretical underpinnings of the MWI's testability.⁵

However, it is mostly questionable whether or not the inherent essence of the MWI is compatible with empirical mechanisms of testability. Strictly speaking, we enquire if or not there exists an experimental machinery that is essentially capable of recognizing the parallel worlds from each other. If the answer is positive then we would be eager to know if or not such a machinery is practically implementable. Still, if we receive a negative response we would be confident that the untestability of the MWI is an unavoidable part of its nature and no practical endeavor to test the validity of the

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¹ See [8, 31] for a thorough introduction to the history of Everett's theory.

² In this paper, the term "experimentalism" is substantially used in the sense of "empiricism", the experience-based approach of experimentalism.

³ We must remark that there is at least a feasible test for the MWI known as Deutsch's version of Wigner's friend experiment [13]. Although the experiment is theoretically applicable, it necessitates technology that is currently unavailable, such as a quantum computer. In this thought experiment the MWI predicts a different outcome compared to the collapse theory. For other proposals of such experiments and more discussions due see [23, 42].

⁴ See [9, 10, 13, 15, 18, 22, 28, 29, 32, 35, 42, 47, 48] for various understandings of the MWI.

⁵ See [2, 3, 13, 15, 24, 42] and the references therein for more arguments about the problem.

interpretation would be successful. In this regard, we will show that even if one can introduce an empirical criterion for testing the credence of the MWI assumptions it would not work properly in distinguishing the parallel worlds based on the observations of the measurements.

Indeed, the main shortcoming of the MWI as a philosophical/theoretical interpretation of quantum mechanics - which is inherently based on statistical aspects of subatomic phenomena - is that it provides no appropriate connection to the inherent empirical essence of quantum theory. More precisely, a physical theory with statistical foundations must provide a chance of the existence of experimental errors in the fundamental formalism of the theory, whilst it can be shown that there is no such possibility in the empirical presumptions of the MWI. For example, we recall that in the Copenhagen interpretation, the Born rule or the uncertainty principle provides basic flexibility to the empirical assessments of the theory, because they substantially admit experimental errors in their theoretical formulation.

However, as a deterministic theory, the MWI has the minimum tolerance against deviated data, since the empirical aspects of the interpretation have the least connection to statistical concepts and the inherent deviated data, even less than classical mechanics. In other words, the MWI endeavors to provide a continuous mechanism for the evolution of the universal wave function by discarding the wave function collapse in the measurement postulate, but it fails in conducting the theory to its empirical aspects due to the inevitable existence of the experimental errors which allegedly have no predicted role in the interpretation. Because of the inherent existence of experimental errors, there would be no confident mechanism to show us whether an unexpected observation is due to the entrance to a certain parallel world or a wrong outcome caused by the nature of the experiment. Just when we try to incorporate such scrutinies in the study of the MWI ontology, we realize that no contribution has been considered for the empirical aspects such as experimental errors in fundamental assumptions of the interpretation.

In principle, the contribution of experimental errors is invaluable in the MWI, since each one can cause a fatal misunderstanding between two distinct copies of the whole universe. A physical theory is, in fact, a concrete connection between theoretical ideas and experimental observations, and it is still an ambiguous problem how the MWI can fill this extremely wide gap properly. Strictly speaking, as we will show in this paper, any endeavor to check the main claim of the MWI will be fruitless at classical limits when there are numerous consecutive observations in the process. In this case, the significant impacts of inevitable observational errors will not be removed via statistical features but will thoroughly spoil the MWI's claim. In fact, the MWI does not have any certain strategy for admitting and analyzing the deviated data in quantum mechanical measurements and, hence its connection to the laboratory observations, which inherently include experimental errors, is entirely obscured. This significant shortcoming is, in principle, the most critical defect of the MWI separating it from a realistic, testable, and refutable physical theory, since it settles in the deepest intellectual layers of the theory.

In this paper, we will study the mentioned inherent problem of the MWI employing rigorous mathematical approaches. In the first steps, in Sections II and III, we concentrate on two empirical postulates of quantum mechanics, the Born rule and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, and try to figure out their algebraic/ergodic-theoretical effects on the ontological aspects of the MWI. In the next step, in Section IV, we argue the role of the experimental errors in the algebraic/topological

features of the MWI ontology. Finally, in Section V, based on the topological properties of the MWI ontology we will prove that there would be no way to distinguish parallel worlds from each other and the interpretation inherently resists any investigation for such a recognition. In other words, we will show that the MWI will empirically shrink into a single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics in its statistical picture.

II. THE BORN RULE AND THE ONTOLOGY OF THE MWI

Let us start the study by considering the unlimited collection of parallel worlds created in a long-term process of consecutive experiments made by measuring a certain observable \hat{O} on an endless ensemble of a definite quantum state $|\psi\rangle$.⁶ For simplicity, we will assume that \hat{O} has a finite and non-degenerate set of eigenvalues $\{\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{n-1}\}$ with the corresponding set of eigenstates $\{|0\rangle, \dots, |n-1\rangle\}$. Suppose that

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha_0|0\rangle + \dots + \alpha_{n-1}|n-1\rangle \quad (\text{II.1})$$

is the mentioned quantum state with $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |\alpha_i|^2 = 1$. We also assume that $|\psi\rangle$ comprises no special intrinsic structure such as the total symmetry in the possibility of outcomes (i.e. $|\alpha_0|^2 = \dots = |\alpha_{n-1}|^2 = \frac{1}{n}$) or the certainty in the measurement results (i.e. there exists some specific i so that $|\alpha_i| = 1$). Thus, according to the assumptions of the MWI, an infinite sequence of measurements on an endless ensemble of copies of $|\psi\rangle$ will produce an unlimited set of parallel worlds. In this way, a parallel world ω is uniquely recognized by an infinite sequence of numbers in $\{0, \dots, n-1\}$, say $S_\omega = \{a_i\}$, so that $a_i = k$ means observing λ_k in the i -th measurement. The infinite sequence $S_\omega = \{a_i\}$ can be rewritten as a real number in $[0, 1]$ as

$$s_\omega = 0.a_1a_2a_3\dots \quad (\text{II.2})$$

We will refer to (II.2) as the *code* of ω or generally the *world's code*. Strictly speaking, we will consider the world's codes as real numbers in base n . Therefore, the set of world's codes of all created parallel worlds in the explained infinite sequence of consecutive measurements will contain any real number of $[0, 1]$. Therefore, it seems that the set of all created parallel worlds, which we denote by Ω , is in some way identical to $[0, 1]$. However, this identification is not exact and needs more accurate scrutiny.

Remember that in any base n the real numbers in $[0, 1]$ with finite non-zero digits have two distinct representations. In fact, although both sides of the equality of

$$0.a_1\dots(a_k-1)\overline{(n-1)} = 0.a_1\dots a_k\bar{0} \quad (a_k \geq 1) \quad (\text{II.3})$$

depict the same point in $[0, 1]$, the infinite sequences

$$S_{\omega_1} = \{a_1, \dots, a_k - 1, n - 1, n - 1, n - 1, \dots\} \quad \text{and} \quad S_{\omega_2} = \{a_1, \dots, a_k, 0, 0, 0, \dots\} \quad (\text{II.4})$$

⁶ We should emphasize that the endless ensemble and infinite measurements assumed here are idealizations and serious problems of the proposal. However, while such idealizations are not realistic, they are often necessary for theoretical purposes in theoretical physics.

represent two different parallel worlds. Hence, let us split Ω to two disjoint parts:

- 1) Ω_1 , which includes the parallel worlds whose codes terminate with an infinite sequence of $(n-1)s$;
- 2) Ω_2 , which contains the other parallel worlds.

There are two *world's code* maps

$$s_1 : \Omega_1 \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad \text{and} \quad s_2 : \Omega_2 \rightarrow [0, 1) \quad (\text{II.5})$$

each of which assigns the world's code s_ω to the parallel world ω . It is easily seen that both s_1 and s_2 are one-to-one maps, whereas s_2 is onto. In fact, $s_1(\Omega_1)$ comprises the rational numbers in $[0, 1]$ who admit finite non-zero digits in base n . Thus, Ω_1 is a countable set. On the other hand, each element of Ω_2 is uniquely connected to a certain number in $I = [0, 1)$ by the invertible map s_2 . Hence, Ω_2 is uncountable.

According to the assumptions of the MWI declared in [42, 43], the physical experiences of the agents of each parallel world is identical to those of the sentient beings living in the physical world of the single-world interpretations of quantum mechanics. Hence, the agents of the parallel worlds must approve the following two empirical laws statistically:⁷

- i) The Born rule;
- ii) Heisenberg's uncertainty principle.

Throughout the rest of the present section, we will concentrate on the role of the Born rule in the ontological aspects of the MWI,⁸ and postpone the study of the effect of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle on the ontology of the interpretation to the next section.

Based on the above discussions, the probability of observing λ_k in the parallel world ω is given by the eventual density of k in the digits of the world's code s_ω , i.e., if $p_k(s_\omega)$ is the mentioned probability we have:

$$p_k(s_\omega) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{a_i, k}. \quad (\text{II.6})$$

However, in order to approve the Born rule, the agent of the parallel world ω must statistically conclude that:

$$p_k(s_\omega) = |\alpha_k|^2. \quad (\text{II.7})$$

Here, we should specify that the main focus of the present research is to use experimentalist viewpoints to study the MWI, as if the experimental principles of quantum mechanics (including the Born rule and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle) are being discovered/validated along the branches

⁷ One should note that this brief list is not exhaustive, but rather a simple framework for the model presented in this study.

⁸ See [1, 7, 12, 21, 24–27, 30, 37, 40, 41, 46] and the references therein for more discussions about the role and the importance of the Born rule in the MWI.

of the vast forest of parallel worlds, since, in fact, it appears that it happened once over the past century.⁹ Based on this understanding of the MWI, besides the more prevailing and well-known subjective approaches to the Born rule in the MWI (such as the Deutsch-Wallace decision theory [14, 44–46]), the frequentist explanation of the rule, as described in (II.6) and (II.7), has confident rationality in the interpretation.¹⁰

It is obvious that for the general structure of the quantum state (II.1) the equality (II.7) would not be satisfied in all parallel worlds. For instance, if the world's code of the parallel world ω terminates with infinite $k_0 \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, then we obtain from (II.6):

$$p_k(s_\omega) = \begin{cases} 1 & , k = k_0 \\ 0 & , k \neq k_0 \end{cases} . \quad (\text{II.8})$$

Therefore, according to the properties of the quantum state (II.1) the sentient beings of ω will not confirm the Born rule. In particular, all elements of Ω_1 will disapprove of the Born rule statistically. Thus, the collection of the parallel worlds whose sentient beings acknowledge the Born rule is a proper subset of Ω_2 . Let us denote this set by \mathcal{B} which stands for the name of "Born". According to the above argumentation s_2 maps \mathcal{B} to a proper subset of I . It can be seen that \mathcal{B} is a very special set, since based on the Birkhoff's ergodic theorem [5, 6] any set of real numbers in $[0, 1]$ satisfying (II.7) with $|\alpha_k|^2 \neq \frac{1}{n}$ for some k is a Lebesgue null set,¹¹ but, however, upon an old result of Eggleston [4] it will have a positive Hausdorff dimension and hence, uncountable elements. Consequently, \mathcal{B} is both as small as a null set and as large as an uncountable set.

Here, we must recognize that \mathcal{B} is, in fact, the only viable long-term ontology of the MWI from the perspective of the Born rule. This is because any agent residing in a parallel world outside of \mathcal{B} would experience the Born rule differently and thus develop fundamentally distinct understandings of physical reality. Consequently, adopting a frequentist viewpoint of the Born rule within the MWI framework implies that assuming identical physical/statistical experiences for observers across parallel worlds and in any single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics condenses the vast ontology of the MWI to the limited set defined by \mathcal{B} in classical limits over long-term processes.

III. HEISENBERG'S UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE AND THE MWI

Let us have a closer look at the parallel worlds whose agents approve of the Born rule. Assume that ω with infinite sequence $S_\omega = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots\}$ is one of such worlds. Based on (II.6) and (II.7), it is easily seen that any other parallel world ω' with the infinite sequence $S_{\omega'} = \{a'_1, a'_2, a'_3, \dots\}$ which its elements coincide with those of S_ω except for some initials will embrace the Born rule similarly. This concept defines an equivalence relation among parallel worlds: Two parallel worlds ω and ω' with infinite sequences $S_\omega = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$ and $S_{\omega'} = \{a'_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$ are said to be *linearly equivalent* if and only if there

⁹ In this regard, we should cite Vaidman's illustrating comment [42]: "Due to the identity of the mathematical counterparts of worlds, we should not expect any difference between our experience in a particular world of the MWI and the experience in a single-world universe with collapse at every quantum measurement."

¹⁰ See [33–36, 42] for further discussions and comparable viewpoints on the MWI.

¹¹ See also [11] for a nice presentation of Birkhoff's ergodic theorem.

exist integers $p, q \geq 0$ so that:

$$a_{p+i} = a'_{q+i} \quad (\text{III.1})$$

for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Let us show two linearly equivalent worlds ω and ω' with the following notation:

$$\omega \cong_L \omega', \quad (\text{III.2})$$

and denote the linear equivalence class of ω with $[\omega]_L$. As mentioned above, it is obvious from (II.6) that if $\omega \cong_L \omega'$, then:

$$p_k(s_\omega) = p_k(s_{\omega'}), \quad (\text{III.3})$$

for any k . Thus, " \cong_L " is an equivalence relation on \mathcal{B} . However, it is a somewhat special relation since each of its equivalence classes contains only countable parallel worlds.

As we explained, the agents of two linearly equivalent parallel worlds have infinitely many of the same consecutive observations except for a finite number of initial results. Hence, the two linearly equivalent parallel worlds are practically the same physical pictures: No physical effect and information are acknowledged/inferred based on the initial distinct outcomes since they will fade or vanish among infinite consecutive identical observations. In principle, two linearly equivalent worlds are separable only from theoretical viewpoints, whereas there is no well-defined empirical criterion to distinguish them delicately: How can we diagnose that an initial disagreement record arises from the nature of the experiment (e.g. observational errors or deviated data) or the features of the universal wave function and transferring to different parallel worlds? Actually, no empirically possible way exists for such a diagnosis.

We can define another empirically equivalence relation among the parallel worlds of the MWI ontology: Two parallel words are said to be *effectively equivalent* if their agents observe infinitely many consecutive identical outcomes except for a random deviation which has the ultimate density zero. More precisely, two parallel worlds ω and ω' with infinite sequences $S_\omega = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$ and $S_{\omega'} = \{a'_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$ are effectively equivalent if and only if there exists $\mathcal{N} \subset \mathbb{N}$ so that:

a) \mathcal{N} indicates the *random fluctuation set* between S_ω and $S_{\omega'}$, i.e.;

$$\begin{cases} a_i = a'_i, & i \notin \mathcal{N} \\ a_i \neq a'_i, & i \in \mathcal{N} \end{cases}, \quad (\text{III.4})$$

b) The random fluctuation set \mathcal{N} has zero ultimate density, i.e.:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}, i \leq N} 1 = 0. \quad (\text{III.5})$$

Let us show two effectively equivalent worlds ω and ω' with the following notation:

$$\omega \cong_E \omega'. \quad (\text{III.6})$$

It is clearly seen from (II.6) and (III.5) that if $\omega \cong_E \omega'$, then:

$$p_k(s_\omega) = p_k(s_{\omega'}), \quad (\text{III.7})$$

for any k . Therefore, " \cong_E " is also an equivalence relation on \mathcal{B} , which is, in fact, a more powerful relation with respect to " \cong_L ", since based on the Eggleston theorem [4] its equivalence classes are uncountable sets.

In principle, if two parallel worlds are effectively equivalent not only their agents will obtain equal statistical information based on their own observations, but they will also effectively record identical statistics of the measurements. In fact, two effectively equivalent worlds can be separated only from the theoretical point of view, and there is no well-defined experimental mechanism to distinguish them thoroughly: How can we recognize that the random disagreement records arise from the nature of the experiment (i.e. experimental errors and insignificant deviations) or the structure of the universal wave function and transferring to different parallel worlds? Once again, no empirically possible method is available for such a recognition.

Now, we are ready to provide our final definition of equivalent parallel worlds: Two parallel worlds ω and ω' are said to be *empirically equivalent*, and it is denoted by $\omega \cong \omega'$, if and only if there exists a parallel world $\hat{\omega}$ so that:¹²

$$\omega \cong_L \hat{\omega} \cong_E \omega'. \quad (\text{III.8})$$

In fact, (III.3) and (III.7) guarantee that " \cong " is an equivalence relation on \mathcal{B} . We will show the empirical equivalence class of ω by $[\omega]$. In principle, the empirical equivalence relation is the most general and simplest empirical criterion for unifying either the indistinguishable physical experiences/histories in a single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics or the practically equivalent physical worlds in the ontology of the MWI.

Let us now turn to the relevance of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle to this investigation. To study this relationship, we first introduce a well-defined product of parallel worlds. Assume that ω_1 and ω_2 are two parallel worlds with infinite sequences $S_{\omega_1} = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ and $S_{\omega_2} = \{b_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$. We define the product of ω_1 and ω_2 , denoted by $\omega_1 \odot \omega_2$, as the parallel world whose infinite sequence is:

$$S_{\omega_1 \odot \omega_2} = \{a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, a_3, b_3, \dots\}. \quad (\text{III.9})$$

It is easily seen that for each k we have:

$$p_k(S_{\omega_1 \odot \omega_2}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(p_k(S_{\omega_1}) + p_k(S_{\omega_2}) \right). \quad (\text{III.10})$$

Therefore, \mathcal{B} is closed under the product \odot . Now suppose that

$$\omega^N = \underbrace{\omega \odot \dots \odot \omega}_{N \text{ copies}} \quad (\text{III.11})$$

and consider the linear equivalence classes of $[\omega^N]_L$ for each $\omega \in \mathcal{B}$. It is easy to see that the sentient beings of each linear equivalence class $[\omega^N]_L$ with $N \geq 2$ will obtain a semi-deterministic law to predict the next outcome based on the last observation. In principle, they can anticipate N outcomes out of each consecutive $N + 1$ observation with certainty upon their immediately previous results and,

¹² It is easy to see that if $\omega \cong_L \hat{\omega} \cong_E \omega'$, then there will be a parallel world $\tilde{\omega}$ so that $\omega \cong_E \tilde{\omega} \cong_L \omega'$. Hence, the definition (III.8) is equivalent to the existence of finitely many parallel worlds $\omega_1, \dots, \omega_k \in \Omega$ so that: $\omega \cong_{X_0} \omega_1 \cong_{X_1} \dots \cong_{X_{k-1}} \omega_k \cong_{X_k} \omega'$, wherein $X_0, X_1, \dots, X_k \in \{L, E\}$. This shows that " \cong " is a well-defined equivalence relation.

hence, although accept the Born rule, they will refute Heisenberg's uncertainty principle statistically provided N is larger than 1.¹³ It must be emphasized that the predictability of the measurement results is statistically equivalent to the vanishing of the variance of the observations, a fact which contradicts the uncertainty principle. We should also denote that here, we confined the concept of predictability to the simplest deterministic law of prediction that brings up a rule for anticipating an observation based on the outcome of its immediately previous experiment.

As an empirical result any element of the empirical equivalence class $[\omega^N]$ with $N > 1$ will similarly discard the uncertainty principle statistically. Define $\mathcal{A} := \bigcup_{\omega \in \mathcal{B}} \bigcup_{N=2}^{\infty} [\omega^N]$ to be the set of all parallel worlds whose sentient beings acknowledge the Born rule, but disapprove of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. We must emphasize that an agent residing in an equivalence class of \mathcal{A} , such as $[\omega^N]$ for the parallel world ω , develops a fundamentally distinct physical reality. Consequently, \mathcal{R} is the only permissible long-term ontology of the MWI from the perspective of the Born rule and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. Thus, as a quantum mechanical theory, the MWI ontology must be restricted to the set of $\mathcal{R} := \mathcal{B} - \mathcal{A}$, as the collection of all "Realistic" parallel worlds whose agents could have physical experiences identical to the quantum physics of a single-world interpretation. Indeed, \mathcal{R} has common astonishing properties with \mathcal{B} : Once again we can see that \mathcal{R} is both as small as a null set and as large as an uncountable set.¹⁴

IV. EMPIRICALLY EQUIVALENT WORLDS AND THE MWI

Let us concentrate our investigation on various aspects of the MWI ontology from the empirical viewpoints. Firstly, we enquire: What is the main role of measurement errors and accidental results caused by limited laboratory accuracy or the nature of the experiment in the MWI? We are aware that even in the Young double-slit experiment, as one of the simplest quantum mechanical tests, although very rare, a few numbers of photons fall in the forbidden strips, and such defects stem from either the limits of accuracy which would never vanish entirely due to the uncertainty principle or the essence of the experiment which may include insignificant deviated results and unexpected data, hence would not be removed at all. Even if we assume that human errors could be eliminated by employing fault diagnostic techniques and elaborate modern devices/programs like AI, experimental errors that are parts of the nature of the experiments would never be eliminated completely.

Therefore, for studying the empirical aspects of the MWI, we are really enthusiastic about figuring out the position of observational errors and deviated data in the interpretation. In fact, the MWI claim focuses on creating separate parallel worlds in every single observation, while any individual outcome,

¹³ At least the agents of the parallel world $[\omega^N]_L$ with $N > 1$, if believe in some uncertainty principle, they will not accept Heisenberg's statement thoroughly. Hence, the physics that they experience is distinct from what the sentient beings of the physical universe will figure out in a single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics.

¹⁴ Since $\mathcal{R} \subset \mathcal{B}$ it is obvious that $s_2(\mathcal{R})$ is a Lebesgue null set. Thus, to prove the claim we must show that \mathcal{R} is uncountable. To see this let $\omega \in \mathcal{R}$ be an arbitrary parallel world with world's code $s_\omega = 0.a_1a_2a_3 \dots$. Fix $m > 1$ and assume that $\sigma = \{r_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ is an infinite binary sequence comprised of 0 and 1. Now define a new world's code $s_\omega^\sigma = 0.b_1b_2b_3 \dots$ as: $b_{km+i} = a_{km+i}$ if $r_k = 0$, and $b_{km+i} = a_{km+m-i}$ if $r_k = 1$ ($1 \leq i < m$). It is seen that s_ω^σ belongs to $s_2(\mathcal{R})$ (i.e. it satisfies (II.7) and is not included in $s_2(\mathcal{A})$) provided ω is a parallel world in \mathcal{R} . Hence, for almost all σ the parallel world ω^σ of the code s_ω^σ is an element of \mathcal{R} distinct from ω . Since the set of all binary sequences is uncountable there are uncountable worlds ω^σ included in \mathcal{R} , which proves that \mathcal{R} is uncountable itself.

as is considered in statistical studies, may be an insignificant deviated result caused by inaccuracy of the ordering/tuning of the experiment apparatuses or the nature of the measurement. According to the "Oxford Dictionary of Statistical Terms" observational/measurement error is "the difference between a measured value of a quantity and its unknown true value" [16]. Such defects, although inherent in the measurement process, will decay in the statistical assessments of the results, as has been considered in any single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics. However, as explained above, experimental errors will play a crucial role in the MWI as the wrong signals of entrances to new parallel worlds.

More precisely, there exists a confusing ambiguity about the significance of these insignificant results in the MWI: How can we be confident that observing an unexpected result is due to the natural limitation of the experiment (e.g. measurement errors) or a real transferring process to a new parallel world? As we emphasized above, despite the situation in the single-world interpretations of quantum mechanics, the extremely high importance of every single observation in the MWI is a serious obstacle to considering the experimental defects and taming the invalid outcomes within a statistical mechanism of the interpretation. On the other hand, the statistical essence of the most well-understood single-world interpretations of quantum mechanics provides a well-defined connection between the theoretical features and the empirical aspects of the theory. Thus, it seems that the MWI is too theoretical/philosophical to simply connect to the empirical nature of quantum mechanics in laboratories.

To grasp the critical role of the experimental errors in the MWI we design a Gedanken experiment defined by gambling on the world's codes, the so-called *MWI gamble*: There is a predetermined code, the so-called *golden code* so that the winner of the gambling is the agent who records that as his world's code based on the history of his observations. We must assume that the golden code respects the Born rule of (II.7) and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, hence, its world belongs to \mathcal{R} . However, there are some questions about the mechanism of this gambling. For example: How confident are we that there exists a unique parallel world whose agent wins the gamble while observational errors are inevitable parts of the experiment? Because of the observational errors, there may be more than one winner or no one. On the other hand, the golden code is the address of a certain parallel world as the final destination and if the world's codes are recorded with mistakes the agent(s) who report the golden code may not have reached the final destination: How much are we assured that the alleged winner is the real one while it is highly unlikely that an observer would have recorded his world's code without the experimental errors?

So we may inquire: How is it rational to insist fiercely on each individual experimental result while a single outcome may be affected by experimental errors? How does the MWI address the intricate problem of the ill-defined position of the experimental errors in the interpretation? As an example, the Copenhagen interpretation, with all its possible deficiencies, admits the role of observational errors in its essence because of insists on Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and the Born rule as two statistical results.¹⁵ Indeed, incorporating statistical ideas in the empirical aspects of quantum physics is the only key to removing this dilemma. Understanding the indispensable role of statistical nature in an empirical theory like quantum mechanics is the main approach that connects an intuitional sketch

¹⁵ See [38, 39] for two nice presentations of the Copenhagen interpretation.

to a scientific theory, while the pivotal contribution of every single outcome of the experiment in the MWI does not align with this idea. We will see in the following that if we try to provide a statistical explanation for the ontology of the MWI the unrealistic essence of the interpretation would show its own shortcomings clearly.

Upon the above argumentation, the MWI gamble winner can not be determined merely based on the world's code. In particular, identifying a unique agent/world as the winner of the gamble would be a highly error-prone process due to the presence of experimental errors. Rather the only possible way to find the winner is to rely on the statistical information of his world's code. This procedure must be fault-tolerant against any experimental error. That is, the true winner of the MWI gamble could have any world's code that differs from the golden code in some random or insignificant deviated data. Because, if an agent reports such a world's code there would be no empirical way to recognize whether the trajectory his world has passed through the parallel worlds is either that of the golden code but with reporting some random experimental errors among the world's code digits, or of an entirely distinct parallel world that has not reach the final destination truly. Therefore, to have a fair and successful gambling we have no empirically possible choice except to characterize all such indistinguishable parallel worlds by some reliable empirical criteria and introduce all of them as the winner(s).

According to the argumentations of the previous section, if ω_0 is the parallel world of the golden code, then $[\omega_0]$ will be the collection of the worlds that belong to the winner(s) of the MWI gamble. In principle, since the set of the opponents of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle \mathcal{A} is defined based on empirical equivalence classes, the empirical equivalence relation " \cong " is definable on \mathcal{R} and hence, $[\omega_0]$ is a well-defined proper subset of \mathcal{R} . This means that the MWI gamble could be conducted successfully. Moreover, the strategy of the MWI gamble indicates that the empirical equivalence classes have a critical role in the realistic aspects of the MWI from the viewpoint of experimentalism. Indeed, there is no realistic/practical way to distinguish any two empirically equivalent parallel worlds and, therefore, transferring to empirical equivalence classes would be the only way to connect the theoretical ideas of the MWI to realistic aspects of quantum mechanics. Strictly speaking, the quotient set $\bar{\Omega} := \mathcal{R}/\cong$ is the only realistic ontology of the MWI. Our next and final inquiry is whether the elements of $\bar{\Omega}$ are indistinguishable and the MWI gamble will end up successfully.

V. DECAY OF THE MWI TO A SINGLE-WORLD INTERPRETATION

In this section, we try to work out a well-defined characteristic criterion to recognize the winner(s) of the MWI gamble we introduced in the previous section. More precisely, we aim to answer to the question of whether or not the empirical equivalence classes of $\bar{\Omega}$ are practically distinguishable. In principle, the skepticism raised regarding the distinguishability of these equivalence classes is the subject of the investigation that terminates our scrutiny of the ontology of the MWI. We will show that the key to the answer is in the topological structure of \mathcal{R} . We should remind that the restriction of s_2 to \mathcal{R} induces the relative topology of I to \mathcal{R} and this topology is connected to the empirical aspects of the MWI. The next lemma provides invaluable information about the topological structure of \mathcal{R} .

Lemma 1; *Assume that $\omega_0 \in \mathcal{R}$ is the parallel world of the golden code of the MWI gamble. Then, $[\omega_0]$ is a dense subset of \mathcal{R} with respect to the induced topology.*

Proof; Since the world's code map s_2 is invertible, it is enough to show that the image of $[\omega_0]$ under s_2 is dense in $s_2(\mathcal{R})$. Assume that ω is an arbitrary element of \mathcal{R} and has the world's code $s_\omega = 0.c_1c_2c_3\cdots$. We must show that for any $N > 1$ the neighborhood of s_ω with radius $r = \frac{1}{n^N}$ contains a world's code $s_{\omega'}$ whose world ω' belongs to $[\omega_0]$. Let

$$s_{\omega_0} = 0.a_1a_2a_3\cdots \quad (\text{V.1})$$

be the golden code of the winner's parallel world ω_0 , and fix $N \in \mathbb{N}$. Set

$$s_{\omega'} = 0.c_1\cdots c_Na_1a_2a_3\cdots. \quad (\text{V.2})$$

It is obvious that $\omega' \in [\omega_0]$ and $|s_{\omega'} - s_\omega| < \frac{1}{n^N}$. This proves the lemma. **Q.E.D**

Actually, as mentioned above, because of the inevitable role of experimental errors in observation records, any practical criterion for distinguishing two distinct parallel worlds must be given based on the statistical information their sentient beings acknowledged. The way in which we classified the parallel worlds by the empirical equivalence relation based on the linearly and effectively equivalent worlds shows that no single observation is a reliable practical criterion for diagnosing the separation of parallel worlds. Therefore, to distinguish the parallel worlds from each other, we must insist on characteristics that have been extracted based on the statistics/histories of the observations made by their agents regardless of the insignificant deviations due to experimental errors. Any such characteristic criterion is, in fact, given by a function on $\bar{\Omega}$, say $\bar{\phi} : \bar{\Omega} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, for some appropriate m . Equivalently, the characteristic criterion $\bar{\phi}$ can be defined by a function on \mathcal{R} , say

$$\phi : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m, \quad (\text{V.3})$$

which is constant on each empirical equivalence class. In fact, any trustworthy mechanism to recognize the winner(s) of the MWI gamble must be defined based on the characteristic criterion (V.3). But, however, the main question is whether or not such characteristic criteria work properly. Strictly speaking, we inquire if there is any characteristic criterion with the property of

$$\phi(\omega) \neq \phi(\omega_0) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \omega \notin [\omega_0]. \quad (\text{V.4})$$

The following theorem provides the final answer to this inquiry.

Theorem 1; *The characteristic criterion ϕ introduced in (V.3) is a constant function on \mathcal{R} . More precisely, there is no characteristic criterion which can distinguish two separate empirical equivalence classes of parallel worlds in the statistical picture of the MWI by satisfying the property (V.4).*

Proof; It is enough to show that any characteristic criterion ϕ is a continuous function on \mathcal{R} , since based on **Lemma 1** ϕ is constant on the dense subset $[\omega_0]$ and this guarantees that it is constant on the whole of its domain provided it is continuous. For simplicity of the argumentation and working

with real numbers instead of abstract entities like parallel worlds we may consider ϕ as a function on $s_2(\mathcal{R})$, the image of \mathcal{R} under the invertible world's code map s_2 . Thus, we rewrite (V.3) as;¹⁶

$$\phi : s_2(\mathcal{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m. \quad (\text{V.5})$$

However, since ϕ is a statistical characteristic of the parallel worlds its value at each parallel world depends on the statistics/history of the observations of its agent. Hence, the more common history of observations the agents of two parallel worlds ω and ω' have, the closer values ϕ will obtain on their world's codes s_ω and $s_{\omega'}$. More precisely, the more identical initial digits s_ω and $s_{\omega'}$ have, the closer $\phi(s_\omega)$ and $\phi(s_{\omega'})$ are in \mathbb{R}^m . In other words, the closer s_ω and $s_{\omega'}$ are to each other, the smaller $|\phi(s_\omega) - \phi(s_{\omega'})|$ would be too, wherein $|\cdot|$ is the norm of \mathbb{R}^m . Consequently, ϕ must be a continuous function. This finishes the theorem. **Q.E.D.**

Indeed, since $[\omega_0]$ is dense in \mathcal{R} , any finite observation in a parallel world $\omega \in \mathcal{R} - [\omega_0]$ will coincide with the observations that have been made in an element of $[\omega_0]$. That is, for any finite number of measurements the parallel world ω has not yet exited or split from the empirical equivalence class of $[\omega_0]$. Therefore, as far as the statistical structure of the MWI ontology in long-term observation processes is considered there is no empirical chance to separate or distinguish ω from the elements of $[\omega_0]$. Thus, there is no well-defined approach to recognizing the winner(s) of the MWI gamble from the losers. In principle, the statistical interpretation of the MWI eventually leads to an empirically single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics. Hence, if still assumed as a valid expression, the naive ontology of the MWI Ω experiences three consecutive contraction processes: In the first step, Ω must soon shrink to \mathcal{R} by decaying statistically unstable parallel worlds whose agents statistically refute the Born rule and other empirical principles of quantum mechanics such as the uncertainty principle. In the second step, by considering the inevitable role of experimental errors in recording the world's codes \mathcal{R} must be replaced by $\bar{\Omega}$ via transferring to empirically equivalent classes of parallel worlds. Finally, in the third step, $\bar{\Omega}$ has to collapse on a single-world interpretation since its equivalence classes cannot be separated empirically in any finite process of measurements.

Based on the above arguments one may conclude that the ontology of the MWI has nothing to do with the classical experiences in the physical universe since the empirical criteria unify the parallel worlds of the MWI along each long-term process of experiments in classical limits and bring up a monolithic picture that cannot be separated into distinct worlds. Therefore, the experimentalists are encountered to an empirical single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics based on the statistical information of the observations. On the other hand, the MWI gamble fails, since there is no well-defined mechanism to recognize the true winner: Any parallel world in the remnant ontology \mathcal{R} is empirically inseparable from the winner's ω_0 and, hence, its agent is a winner too. This fatal failure establishes that although there would be various possible histories of observations for a definite sequence of measurements, the eventual pictures of such histories are statistically/empirically identical. We interpret this theoretical consequence as the collapse of the MWI on a single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics at classical limits.

¹⁶ In fact, here we replace ϕ by $\phi \circ s_2^{-1}$ but use the same symbol ϕ for simplicity.

VI. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we studied the statistical structure of the ontology of the MWI by employing empirical criteria of the experimentalism viewpoint and mathematical analysis. In the first step, we showed that the MWI ontology must be reduced to an extremely limited set of possible parallel worlds whose sentient beings approve the Born rule. Afterward, we removed the parallel worlds whose agents will not confirm Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and concentrated the investigation on the ontology of parallel worlds which empirically admit both the Born rule and the uncertainty principle. Then, we studied the empirical criteria for distinguishing parallel worlds in the remnant realistic ontology of the MWI by considering the role of the experimental errors in the nature of the measurements. By studying the empirical aspects of the MWI we showed that the main ideas of the MWI are too theoretical/philosophical to be easily connected to the realistic empirical experiences of the classical world, since any consideration of the empirical aspects such as experimental/measurement errors makes the interpretation face serious problems in its inherent essence.

To concentrate our investigation on the empirical viewpoints of experimentalism we defined some equivalence relations for unifying the parallel worlds that their agents obtain thoroughly identical statistical information from their observations. Finally, in **Theorem 1**, we proved that there would be no characteristic criterion defined based on statistical information that could be used for recognizing the equivalence classes of parallel worlds. Hence, we inferred that the ontology of the MWI, if valid, cannot survive for long-term processes, and it must soon reduce to an empirical-based single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics. Therefore, since the classical experiences are based on statistical pictures of a huge number of quantum mechanical observations, we conclude that the MWI, even if it is true at quantum levels, has nothing to do with the classical world and collapses on a single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics at classical limits.

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